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A Study of Silent and Subaltern Voices in Mamang Dai's *The Black Hill* and *Legends of Pensam*

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Abstract:

The Northeastern region of India, particularly its hill communities, has long remained on the margins of the national consciousness – often excluded from the narrative of “mainstream” Indian discourse. The lack of urban centres, challenging terrain, and insurgencies have contributed to stereotypes of the Northeast as “uncivilised”. This marginalisation has been political, social, cultural and intellectual as well. It was through writing that these people got a chance to assert their identity and claim a space within the larger Indian consciousness.

Among the growing community of writers of the Northeast, Mamang Dai stands out as a powerful voice from the state of Arunachal Pradesh. Through her acclaimed works, *The Black Hill* and *Legends of Pensam*, Dai not only gives voices to her people but also brings them into the literary spotlight with their rituals, beliefs, and everyday experiences.

This paper attempts to explore how Dai has given a voice to the subaltern tribes of Arunachal Pradesh with a special focus on the womenfolk of the community.

Keywords: Subaltern, Tribes, History, Women, Identity.

Acclaimed author Mamang Dai, in her books *The Black Hill* and *The Legends of Pensam*, presents the rich cultural tapestry of the tribal communities living in the mountainous regions of Arunachal Pradesh, particularly focusing on the Adi and Mishmee tribes. Through rereading of British recorded histories and her knowledge from the oral tradition of the tribal people, Dai gives a voice to these voiceless and long-ignored tribes – the subalterns.

Studies on the subaltern began around 1982. It was started by Ranajit Guha but was soon joined by other scholars like Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak and Dipesh Chakraborty. These scholars wanted to give voice to the groups of people who have been looked down upon and neglected throughout history.

The idea of the subaltern was primarily referred to by the Italian Marxist political protestor Antonio Gramsci in his article 'Notes on Italian History', which was later published as part of his most extensively acknowledged book, *Prison Notebooks*, written between 1929 and 1935. Gramsci used the term "subaltern" to refer to the underclass in a society, groups that are subjected to the hegemonic power and influence of the dominant classes. The term 'subaltern' also refers to inferior status or rank; subordinate, hence of rank, power, authority and action. In general, subaltern classes include peasants, workers, and other groups who have been denied access to 'hegemonic' power. Subaltern Studies extended into the literary arena as the Subaltern Studies Group, or Subaltern Studies Collective, which was launched around the early 1980s by a group of eminent Indian scholars. Predominant thinkers essentially associated with the same, especially in the context of Indian literature, are Ranajit Guha, Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak, and Dipesh Chakrabarty.

The main objective of these Indian scholars was to reclaim and represent history for the underclass, whose voices had not been heard earlier. Scholars of the Subaltern group hoped to break away from the histories of the elites and Eurocentric bases or biases of existing imperial

history in the case of Southeast Asia, predominantly in the context of India. Guha, in his argument, tries to analyse what the Indians did on their own beyond the effort and authority of the leaders and institutions of the colonial regime and nationalist elite politics. The subaltern, according to him, represents the demographic difference between the total Indian population and all those whom we have described as the elite. According to Spivak, 'subaltern' means to be removed from all lines of social mobility. Spivak was highly critical of the current histories of India that were told from the vantage point of the colonisers. Though the major proponents of the concept, that is, Ranajit Guha, Gayatri Spivak and Dipesh Chakrabarty, have slightly different ways of viewing the same, they were together in their attempt to reread and rethink history from the perspective of the marginalised or the 'other' and give them a voice in the process.

The British people colonised India for a very long period of time, thus creating a hegemonic structure by identifying themselves as the superior and the Indians as inferior, barbaric and uncivilised in every possible way. India as a country was considered an "infantile civilisation" by the colonisers. Due to this process of colonisation by the British, the people of India became marginalised in their own country. However, it can be said that some particular groups of Indians themselves are guilty of making the same differences or distinctions on the basis of caste, class, gender, ethnicity, religion, race, etc. since ages ago. The Dalits (earlier termed as the Untouchables by the upper class), women of all castes and classes, and the northeastern states are some of the many groups of people who suffered the neglect and cruelty of the so-called superior people of the society for very long. And Spivak says that in post-colonial terms, everything that has limited or no access to cultural imperialism is subaltern.

The northeastern states, that is, Assam, Arunachal Pradesh, Meghalaya, Manipur, Mizoram, Nagaland, Sikkim and Tripura, have been since time immemorial rich in their culture, customs, oral tradition and folklore. However, due to its unique topographical

structure, the northeastern region is geographically secluded from the rest of India. The location and distance from mainland India led to an idea that hailing from the northeastern region is a distinct identity distinguishable from what is popularly known as the 'mainstream' Indian. And due to this very assumption, the people in the northeastern states were marginalised politically, socially, culturally, and intellectually; the Northeast was considered as backward. This negligence from the centre gave rise to angst, distrust and political turbulence among the natives, and the literature produced was perceived as writings with terrorism, death, disaster, anger, hatred and rebellion as main themes. This is only partially true, and it was only in the last decade or so that the vibrant contemporary writing from the Northeastern region written in many languages including English, really began to reach the rest of India and other parts of the world. Acclaimed contemporary writers like Robin S Ngangom, Rita Chowdhury, Mamang Dai, Kynpham Sing Nongkynrih, Easterine Kire, Mitra Phukan, Temsula Ao, Linthoi Chanu, Aruni Kashyap, Mamoni Raisom Goswami, Janice Pariat, and Hiren Gohain are some of the many writers from the Northeast region who have proved time and again that literature from this region of the country is much more than what the mainstream society assumes it to be.

Author Mamang Dai's works glorify the mountainous landscape, the various tribes living there, and the customs, traditions, beliefs and folklore of the 'Land of the Rising Sun' - Arunachal Pradesh, also known as the 'Land of Dawn-lit Mountains'. Hailing from the same place, Dai is firmly rooted in the soil of her birthplace. Her works, be it poetry, fiction or non-fiction, always put focus on the rivers, mountains, trees, jungles, rituals, legends, mythology, dances, villages and prayer flags of her dear abode, Arunachal Pradesh. One of the most influential feminist writers of recent times, she not only holds the privilege of being the first woman from the state to be selected for the Indian Administrative Service, but she is also the first from Arunachal Pradesh to be conferred with the Padma Shri for her contribution to literature and education in the year 2011, becoming the glory for the womenfolk of the tribal

state. Her writing conveys an idea of a new literary tradition that has been born in Arunachali literature as well as in Indian English fiction. She also received the prestigious Sahitya Academy award for her novel *'The Black Hill'* in the year 2017.

Dai's book *'The Black Hill'* (2011) is a historical fiction based on the disappearance of a French Jesuit priest, Fr Nicolas Krick, from the Paris Foreign Missions, who was looking for a way into Tibet to set up a mission there. It begins with his journey, which led him into Mishmi territory in Arunachal Pradesh. The story also revolves around the tribal chief Kajinsha and his lover and later wife, Gimur. The story is set in 19th-century colonial Arunachal Pradesh (one of the divisions of the erstwhile North East Frontier Agency).

Legends of Pensam (2006) is another remarkable work by Dai. Structurally, this book can be considered neither a novel nor a short story collection, such is the creative imagination of Dai. This book is a collection of short stories in a continuous form narrated by an unnamed narrator. The stories speak of the traditions, customs, and beliefs of the Adi tribes of the snow-capped mountains of Arunachal Pradesh:

In our language, the language of the Adis, the word 'pensam' means 'in-between'. It suggests the middle, or middle ground, but it may also be interpreted as the hidden spaces of the heart where a secret garden grows. It is the small world where anything can happen and everything can be lived; where the narrow boat that we call life sails along somehow in calm or stormy weather; where the life of a man can be measured in the span of a song. (Dai)

Dai, in her novel, *The Black Hill*, attempts to give us a glimpse into the culture of the Adi (then Abor) and the Mishmee tribes, their harmonious lifestyle in the hills, and how their lives turned upside-down with the advent of the British. She basically presents the pre-independence scenario of the northeastern region, the first encounter of the tribes with the colonisers and their

fierce resistance to protect their land and community. The female protagonist, Gimur, belongs to the Abor (now, Adi) tribe from the village of Mebo; the male protagonist, Kajinsha, belongs to the Mishmee tribe from the Mishmee hills; and the French priest Nicholas Krick comes to the northeastern part of India for a South Tibet mission through the territories of the tribes to reach Tibet – “A man, woman and a priest – this is their story” (Dai).

Similarly, in her book, *Legends of Pensam*, Dai, through an intricate web of stories, presents to us the life of the Adis of the Siang Valley steeped in their customs, oral traditions, myths, history and tribal beliefs. Like the majority of tribes inhabiting the central belt of Arunachal, the Adis practise an animistic faith that is woven around forest ecology and coexistence with the natural world. There are few road links in their territory. Travel to the distant villages still entails cumbersome river crossings, elephant rides, and long foot marches through dense forest or over high mountain passes. But the old villagers who walk miles every day say: “When you look at the land you forget your aches and pains” (Dai, 9).

These people love the way they lead their lives. Surrounded by the deep turbulent rivers, rugged terrain, evergreen forest, lofty mountain ranges, flora and fauna, hunting for food, and agriculture, that is, living amidst nature, was what they loved and did since time immemorial. They are self-reliant, and music and dance are a way of life. They have rich oral traditions which were passed down to generations by songs and dance. They are content with their traditional way of living life:

The dancers sigh and wipe their eyes. The fire burns brightly and the shaman is a shadow man leaping up larger than life. He has sung of the beginning of the world; of the sword of five metals that ignited the bonfire of the villages. He has sung the story of his brother, the one who killed a man and became a martyr; the story of the

hawk woman who defied a community to live in a house by the river. These are the stories, rhapsodies of time and destiny, that he must guard (Dai, 55).

Be it the Abor tribes or the Mishmee tribes, these tribal people have been living harmoniously among the rivers and mountains. Their land is their God. “And what falls from the sky – rain, thunder and lightning - are also voices of spirits telling us something...” (Dai, 140) The narrator in Dai’s *Legends of Pensam* also says that for Hoxo, “...the colour green soothed him. It was the colour of escape and solitude...” (Dai, 8).

Through the use of historical records, Dai’s extensive research on her own, her knowledge of her tribal history and their lifestyle, and her creative use of imagination, Dai gives a voice to the tribes to present their side of the story independent of the British recorded histories.

The very first chapter of the book, titled ‘The Arrival of Strangers’ in *The Black Hill*, indicate the coming of the British, that is, the Migluns: “Everyone had heard about the British, the White men – the miglun- who were coming upriver towards Mebo in long boats. They wanted a meeting with the villagers to talk about establishing a trading post a few miles downstream...” (Dai, 3).

The colonisers’ only goal was to conquer, extract the natural resources of the country, and benefit themselves and their own land. The involvement of the British in the Anglo-Burmese War of 1824 and the signing of the Yandabo Treaty in 1826 led to Assam coming under the control of the British Government. And with this, slowly and gradually the British gaze turned to the hills. Moreover, the fact that there existed various overland routes to China, Tibet and Burma through the territories of these tribes attracted enough attention of the British to this part of the country. For a profitable trans-Himalayan trade through the Arunachal areas, pacification of the tribal people was necessary, according to them. And when the British began

eyeing their land, it was an obvious reaction on their part to resist against them. "...since the British had occupied Assam, their hills had been disturbed by these strange, foreign men who crept deeper and deeper into their land carrying gifts of salt, iron, tobacco and opium..." (Dai, 8).

It was not that there was complete peace among the tribes. Living in isolation, the tribes living in one valley viewed the other tribe living across with suspicion and dread. Claims over land, ownership rights to hunt and fish, rivers and streams often led to bloody, inter-tribal feuds, and no one knew when the fighting would end. Even when the British arrived in these areas, the small gifts that they would bring along with them lured some of the tribal people towards them. This gave in to more enmity among some tribes. But for most tribal clans, they shared the same hatred for the British and feared being brought under their control. Thus, these people put up a united front to resist the coming of the British. Dai in *The Black Hill* sheds light on the same:

In 1839 news reached him of a plot by the Khampti clans of Suddya in Assam to rise up against the British. Their chief, who went by the title of Suddya Khawa Gohain, had been stripped of his title and dignity by the British authorities and removed from his position. He sent out a call for help. It was a chance Kajinsha's father could not miss. In the dead of night he led a group of men south to the Khampti villages dotted around the banks of the Burhampooter River. They joined hands with 500-armed Khampti warriors who advanced on the British station from all directions. In the surprise attack the British Political Agent, Colonel Adam White, and his forces numbering some eighty men were butchered and all but two sepoy lines burned to the ground. In the fighting Kajinsha's father had been fatally wounded. 'I saw the white people running' he had said (Dai, 9).

Here, Dai specially stresses the fact that ‘the white people ran’. Through her narration she not only shows the struggles of the tribes in resisting the British entry into their land but also points to the fact that these struggles on the part of the tribes were never recorded in Indian history.

Father Nicholas Krick came all the way from France to spread the message of Jesus, the saviour. He wanted to carry the gospel to the unknown parts of the world, and more than that, he was seeking an experience of the passionate union with the Divine. And he knew this union would happen only through the path of love and service. Therefore, when he arrived in the northeastern region of India, unlike other ‘migluns’, taking over the land of the tribes was not something he had in mind. But because he was white, no matter what, he had to go through several difficulties along the way – from being looted by some of the natives, being sent back from Tibet, hunger, illness, and the arduous journey back and forth - he suffered a lot. Yet, he never gave up, and his genteel manners made Kajinsha and Lendem believe in him. They understood that this white man, or ‘miglun’, was not like the other migluns. He was there to spread love and healing, the message of his God. But there were also people like Marpa who never could put their belief in the white men. And it was because of Marpa’s conspiracy in the story that got both the priest Father Krick and Augustine Bourry killed.

The actual reason for the disappearance of the two priests are not fully recorded.

The records are also unclear about whether the condemned man killed one or two prison guards while awaiting his sentence. The ravages of time, flood, fire, have destroyed many important government documents of the time, especially those that were housed in Sadiya and Dibrugarh (Dai, 293).

In the story, Dai presents Kajinsha as a victim of conspiracy. He had not gone to kill the priest; rather he went there to save the priest from Marpa and Lamet. But he is evicted as the

one who killed the priest and his friend based on the rumours spread among the people in the hills by the conspirators. This retake of history by Dai shows her urgent attempt to reverse the British representation of the tribes. Also, it is to be noted that she shows the execution of Kajinsha not as an act of justice for killing the Priest and his friend but because of his resistance against the British. Arresting Kajinsha gave the British a solid reason to get entry into the until-now isolated and feared Mishmee territory.

This was the first punitive expedition against the Mishmee and no doubt Eden and his men were able to achieve this feat with the assistance of some villagers who showed them the way perhaps under pressure or due to local rivalry amongst the different clans. It was a great show of British might and authority (Dai, 264).

In *Legends of Pensam* too, Dai presents the scenario that came to life with the advent of the British. The British wanted a labour force from various hill tribes to work for them. The elders of the tribal villages were given the duty to persuade able-bodied men to join the workforce:

The men recruited from the hills were given rations and bedding but the work was the work of the devil. Those who went and returned said the forest and the skies were like nothing they had seen before. The migluns were terrifying in their energy and determination. In the lashing rain and the wet earth that buried men up to their waists they drove elephants to cross rivers, remove logs and trample the jungle. The elephants strained and quivered to the shouts of their mahouts, slipped, struggled, knelt, struggled on, and many of the poor animals lost their footing and hurtled off the mountainside bellowing like mythical beasts with their eyes rolled up skywards. It was unimaginable, what the migluns were trying to achieve. In the swampy valleys men died like flies, shivering with fever and fear (Dai, 39).

Dai also mentions the building of the mysterious Still-well Road that wound through Asia like a giant serpent. She states that no other road in the world had taken as high a toll of human lives as this one; it has also been named – ‘A-man-a-mile-road’.

Another historical event that Dai has mentioned in both the books is the Abor Expeditionary Field Force of 1912. The first expedition happened during 1893-94 which was vehemently fought by the tribes. The second expedition occurred during 1912:

In 1911, a British political officer set out from the plains of Assam on a mission to explore the course of the river Siang flowing through the territory of the Adis. Noel Williamson was well known in the region, with twenty years of experience in dealing with the tribes in the hill tracts of the country. This time, however, his tour ended in tragedy. An angry Adi struck him down in the village of Komsing. Other men of his tribe joined him and then there was a massacre. No one is quite sure what provoked the attack. Some recorded evidence suggests a communication gap: the tribe feared that Williamson would bring troops to destroy its villages. Another version says that the white sahib had insulted a man who later followed him to Komsing and killed him. There are also accounts that tell of a scandal some years before this attack—a story of seduction and romance between a local woman and another white man following the course of the river. He had made her reckless, and fearless like a hawk, and the tribe had meted out terrible punishment in retaliation. Perhaps it was the memory of this event that was the cause. Everything is conjecture. What is certain is that besides Williamson and his friend, a tea-garden doctor named Dr Gregorson, forty-seven sepoy and coolies were also killed. Only three men survived to tell the tale. News of the massacre sent shockwaves across colonial India and resulted in the punitive expedition of 1912, which became known as the Abor Expeditionary Field Force (Dai, 47).

Irrespective of the reasons behind the killing, the voiceless Adi tribe were overpowered by the strength of the British, and ultimately, they surrendered. "Surrender is a kind of peace. The men of the village closed their eyes and recalled the symbols of peace: a broken arrow, a bent sword; the penitence of men who cut their bowstrings and threw down their spears to the ground". (Dai, 53)

The word 'Abor' as mentioned in the book, *The Black Hill*, was not used by the tribes living near the Siang River. Even before the British, it was plains people who used the word 'Abor', which meant 'barbarous', 'independent', 'savage' or 'wild tribe'. This term was literally forced on these people because of the manner in which the Abors were imagined by the valley state as well as by the colonial opinions - the way in which their territorial and geographical spaces were identified and mapped by the colonial officials, and the way their culture, civilisation, and social world were enquired into, explored, examined, and written.

A very important point to be noted is that Dai, through both these works, has not only tried to give voice to the men who have been voiceless or neglected for so long but also to the womenfolk as well.

The character of Gimur in *The Black Hill* is a perfect example. Dai states that 'there is not a trace of her in any record of the period'. Yet, her presence in the story is extremely significant. From the very beginning of the book, we see she was somewhat different in her ways of living. When her mother would ask her to hide her face among men or any other such restrictions, she never paid any heed to any. She was well aware of what she wanted in her life, unlike most girls of her age who lived life according to the social constructs of the patriarchal society that they lived in. She did not give in to the norms that society had made only for women. She had a voice and a mind of her own. Not only was she an expert in the household chores that confined the womenfolk to their homes all their lives, but she was also bold and

fearless in every way possible. Even though she knew the consequences of her eloping with a man of another tribe, she did so as she was in love with Kajinsha. Every time the priest saw her, he was reminded of Bellona, the Roman goddess of war. She had done the unthinkable. She was the female warrior who had crossed rivers and mountains carrying a bright banner of love with Kajinsha. And when she realised her love was not respected, that her husband cheated on her behind her back, she did not suffer in silence. She took the same arduous journey to come back to her village, knowing quite clearly the insults that she might have to face. In that journey, she even lost her child, yet she stayed calm and strong and continued to live in silence. She had the heart to try to save her husband, who was locked up in the known jail of Dibrugarh (then, Debroogurh). When she was mocked at by a prison guard there for being a woman, she killed him. “What am I? Am I not one of the choosen, she thought. Am I not God’s creation? A woman is God’s creation! ... here she was standing inside prison walls and staring at the man she loved more than life and God...this is love. My love draws blood” (Dai, 281). Gimur continued living for Kajinsha even after his death because he had asked her to. But she stopped speaking forever, living in silence with all her pain. Yet she lived a life like a warrior.

Nenem from *Legends of Pensam* is another example. She was known for her extraordinary beauty and was remembered as the woman who fell in love with a British officer. She was known to be of a quiet demeanour but with an impulsive streak that was unpredictable; ‘Like the river’, people said. Nenem, too, had the courage to do what she wanted. She was capable of doing anything if baited or prevented from doing what she wanted. When she fell in love with a white man, she didn’t care about what her people would do or say. Their love for each other made her feel alive and full of power. And when it was time for David, the white officer, to leave for his country, she did not go away with him. She loved her family and her dear friends; she loved her land that was surrounded by forests, rivers and mountains. She could never leave all of it behind. After David left, every night Nenem said to herself, “No one dies

of love. I loved him, and now I am enough on my own". (Dai, 109). She married Kao because she understood that Kao would be a good husband. She did not forget David, but by marrying Kao, she gave herself the chance to love someone again and also be loved by him.

In both the books, Dai, alongside the main plot, shed light on the plight and struggles of women. In the section 'Daughters of the village' of *Legends of Pensam*, she presents the hardships tribal women had to go through every day:

They have been in the forest all morning, cutting wood, cracking dry bamboo and piling stray branches seasoned by sun and rain into stacks to be carried back to the village. This is a daily necessity. The work is hard, but scouring the forest the women could at least stop, stretch, talk to each other. Now the unforgiving hill permits no speech. Every muscle, every trembling cell of the body is concentrated on the effort to tackle the gradient. One step after another they move, silent, with no other thought than to reach the top where they will tear the heavy baskets off their backs for a while and wait, bent and panting, for their bursting hearts to quieten, slowly, slowly, before tackling the last incline to the village gate (Dai, 73).

In this chapter, Dai shows how the womenfolk dealt with their lives. Women like Arsi kept living on with the hardships even though she cursed her forefathers for having come to a place like this – the isolated hills, where she could not even make a flower garden: "Hai! Why? Why do we have to kill ourselves like this? Is this a life? Is this all there is? How can it be!" (Dai, 74).

The narrator in this book could not take the hardships of their daily routine. After the death of her mother, she thought she should stay back in her village, but she could not take the load for long. She therefore settled in a nearby town of Gurdum, which was half a day's journey by road from the village where her mother was buried, yet far enough to still hope for a life of

her own. There were elder women, who had lived life with men who left them for some other women as it was apparently okay for men to have as many women as they wanted in their lives, be it as a wife or not. These women lived and died longing for love and in solitude. Mona, the narrator's friend, was an independent and successful woman. She is a proprietor of the glossy magazine "Diary of the World". Yet, she was still under a patriarchal society that kept blaming women for every other wrong happening. When her daughter Adela was found to be suffering from autism, her husband, though being an educated person, blamed it on her, as if it was because Mona being a working woman that their daughter had contracted the illness.

In *The Black Hill*, we see how there were also women like Chomu, who was used by her own Uncle Marpa just as he pleased. Auli was Kajinsha's first wife yet never got the love and care she deserved. She was being married off to Kajinsha to make ties between the families strong, and Kajinsha married her because he had no other option at that time. Yet it can't be denied that he backed off from his responsibility as a husband.

Dai, by presenting the lives of these women characters, gives a voice to the otherwise voiceless and neglected women. Gender is a social construct, and women have been paying the price of this social construct for ages. Anyone being marginalised in any form on the basis of anything is a subaltern. Dai here creates a space for the womenfolk who are otherwise suppressed in the patriarchal society. She gives them the identity that they are almost always denied, confined to their homes all their lives. Women coming from all kinds of backgrounds, especially in India, have been taught since time immemorial that women are supposed to be the homemaker and not the breadwinner. They are supposed to be married off while they are young, to look after her family and children and keep her husband happy. A custom of these tribal people that Dai brings to light is the custom of bride price. "Every girl is an asset to her family, and a man taking her away in marriage must compensate her parents for depriving them of a daughter" (Dai, 45). This is a custom which we also see among the Igbo tribe of Africa in

Chinua Achebe's *Things Fall Apart* (1957). This custom of the tribes stands in sharp contrast to the custom of the mainland, where the custom of dowry was more relevant.

The British, when they came to the northeastern part of India, had this idea that they were better equipped with technology, civilised and educated, unlike the natives; they were superior in every aspect. This idea was fuelled by the fact that there were sharp differences in the lifestyle, language, food habits, etc. between the people of mainland India and the tribes living in the hills. Not possessing the knowledge of the various tribal languages, a large part of the basic information on the various tribes of the northeast frontier was gained through the inhabitants of the valley. Some of these valley people also acted as interpreters. So, it would not be wrong to say that the first-hand information of the tribes that the colonisers got was not free of biases. And these British official records and their letters to their family are the only source of information concerning the tribes of the northeast, where the tribes were always presented as 'wild' or 'savage' and required pacifying. These indigenous/primitive inhabitants were neither eliminated nor quite absorbed by the rising civilisation in the course of history. For example, although India's tribes have been studied intensively (and extensively) for many decades, both before and after independence, they appear as obscure as ever. While they have often been glorified (particularly by older-generation anthropologists), their popular image has remained rather vague, indifferent, and indeed, full of misconceptions and folklore. Despite the substantial accumulation of literature (official and non-official alike) on the (relative) vulnerability of tribes, despite countless laws enacted for protecting their rights, they remain the "most underdeveloped community"; also, not to forget that half of the country's mineral and forest resources are situated in the tribal areas. All this clearly reflects a resolute ambivalence on the part of the Indian state towards tribes. Dai, therefore, makes it a point to present the rich oral tradition of the tribal people, wherein the shamans, the rhapsodists preserve

the struggles of the tribesmen and women and their culture through songs and dance performances.

There is an absence of authentic histories, and thus writers like Dai have taken it upon themselves to re-present an alternate history in order to preserve the struggles of their earlier generations and the culture and tradition which have been slowly and gradually fading in the ravages of modern times. But most importantly, they undertake this work of presenting an alternate history to give a space, a voice, and an identity to the marginalised.

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